

A Multi-agent Simulation Tool for Micro-scale Contagion Spread Studies

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Abstract—Within the disaster preparedness and emergency response community, there is interest in how contagions spread person-to-person at large gatherings and if mitigation strategies can be employed to reduce new infections. A contagion spread simulation module was developed for the Incident Management Preparedness and Coordination Toolkit that allows a user to see how a geographically accurate layout of the gathering space helps or hinders the spread of a contagion. The results can inform mitigation strategies based on changing the physical layout of an event space. A case study was conducted for a particular event to calibrate the underlying simulation model. This paper presents implementation details of the simulation code that incorporates agent movement and disease propagation. Elements of the case study are presented to show how the tool can be used.

Keywords—*contagion modeling and simulation; epidemiology; incident management; emergency preparedness and response; geographic information system; data fusion*

I. INTRODUCTION

Epidemiological studies often focus on regional populations in the aggregate for the benefit of informing public health policy [1]. In this paper, the interest is in simulating mass gatherings such as conferences or festivals at a single site [2]. The idea to be explored is whether the physical layout of the meeting space can be altered to combat the spread of a contagion that is passed person-to-person. It seems reasonable that if the number and duration of inter-personal contacts can be lowered, the spread of a contagion can be slowed. A requirement of any simulation tool used in this case is the need for accurate geospatial information.

Developed by the U.S. Department of Energy Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), the Incident Management Preparedness and Coordination Toolkit (IMPACT) can be used by a health practitioner who may not have the budget or training to use commercial Geographic Information System (GIS) products targeted at the dedicated GIS professional [3]. In addition, it aims to overcome some of the shortcomings of web browser offerings such as the lack of ability to add local

content and the requirement for constant network access which may be problematic in the field. Funded by the U.S. Department of Homeland Security (DHS) and the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), IMPACT has evolved to become a free, all-hazards software suite. Although IMPACT can be used for many functions, the focus of this paper is on its use in simulating contagion spread at mass gatherings.

II. DESIGN

A contagion spread module was added to the IMPACT suite to implement a Susceptible-Exposed-Infectious-Recovered (SEIR) model [4]. When the simulation starts, a number of agents are generated with properties to be described below. Their behavior and movement are governed by program logic which can be influenced in part by the user. The first of four parameter dialogs is shown in Fig. 1 which governs the simulation time step and duration. Periodic screen captures may be saved and turned into a movie for later playback at faster than real time to facilitate seeing patterns in the agent movement.

An environment must first be constructed using the mapping tool within IMPACT. The user first draws an enclosure in which the simulation will take place. Agents are constrained to move within this space. Optional features called attraction points may be added around which the agents will cluster for a period of time. Without these attraction points, the movement of the agents is completely random. This forms the basis for comparing so-called directed motion to uniform mixing. Fig. 2 shows the input parameter dialog for the agents while Fig 3 shows the dialog for the attraction points. The use of these values is discussed below.

When a simulation starts, a random number generator is seeded with the current time so that no two simulations run the same. A number of agents specified by the user are generated and attributes are assigned, such as their uniformly random (x,y) starting position within the enclosure. One agent is randomly designated as the infectious seed and has its level of

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Fig. 1. General settings for contagion spread simulation.

infectiousness set by adjusting its time of initial infection to occur in a random fashion before the start of the simulation [5]. The duration of infectiousness for each agent is determined individually from a log-normal distribution using the input parameters shown in Fig. 4. For this study, parameters were chosen based on empirical results [6] [7].

During each time-step of the simulation each agent's properties are updated. If the agent is currently waiting at an attraction, it does not move until the dwell time has expired, otherwise it moves towards the next attraction (directed motion). If no attractions are present, movement is random (uniform mixing). Collision detection is implemented by breaking up the enclosure into cells approximately 1 square meter and keeping track of occupied cells. Logic also keeps each agent inside the enclosure and clear of any obstacles (cutouts) introduced by the user when building the environment.

The test for transmission ($S \rightarrow E$) requires each agent to keep track of the time they have been within the minimum contact distance (e.g., 2 meters) of their neighbors. If a

Fig. 3. Attraction (cluster points) settings for contagion spread simulation.

Fig. 2. Agent (people) settings for contagion spread simulation.

neighbor steps out of the contact zone, its timer is reset. If a neighbor within the contact zone is infectious, the probability of transmission is governed by,

$$p_i = 1 - \exp\{-k[F(t_i + d_i) - F(t_i)]\} \quad (1)$$

where k is a probability transmission constant chosen empirically to match the setting, and $F(x)$ is the cumulative distribution function of the log-normally distributed virus shedding schedule,

$$F(x) = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc}\left(-\frac{\ln x - \mu}{\sigma\sqrt{2}}\right) \quad (2)$$

where μ and σ are the virus shedding schedule location and scale. The time values t_i and d_i represent the start time and duration in days of the interaction between agents.

Once exposed, there is a latency period assigned that determines the start of infectiousness that follows an exponential distribution. So the probability that virus shedding

Fig. 4. Contagion settings for contagion spread simulation.

begins before time t is given by the cumulative distribution function,

$$F(t; r) = \begin{cases} 1 - \exp(-rt) & : t \geq 0 \\ 0 & : t < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where t is the time in days, and r is the rate (day^{-1}).

At the end of the latency period, the agent becomes infectious ($E \rightarrow I$) with an infectious period assigned from a log-normal distribution. Once this infectious period expires, the agent recovers ($I \rightarrow R$). All of the distributions follow those outlined in [6]. The simulation stops when all of the agents have recovered or when the user-specified simulation time has been reached.

III. EXAMPLES

Fig. 5 shows a simulation environment that might represent an outdoor marketplace. The enclosure may be seen as well as the optional attraction points which could represent vendor stalls. Cutouts in the enclosure represent obstacles that the agents have to maneuver around. These elements may be hidden to reduce visual clutter when running the simulation.

An example of directed motion is seen in Fig. 6. The agents are color-coded to show their state (S – green, E – yellow, I – red, R – blue). Also, the track of the infectious seed may be displayed (magenta path). The agents will circulate to the various attraction points and spend a random amount of time at each using the input parameter limits. Contrast this with Fig. 7 which shows the scene without any attraction points resulting in uniform mixing. Here the agents mill about randomly.

When the allotted simulation time is up or all of the agents have been infected, the simulation stops and statistics are presented as shown in Table I. The most interesting values are the number of secondary infections, mean number of contacts, and mean cumulative contact time. By modifying the physical meeting space, it may be possible to reduce the number and/or duration of the contacts which will influence the number of secondary infections. This must be explored manually by the user.

TABLE I. Simulation Output for Directed Motion

Total Simulation Time = 1:00:00
Total Wall Time = 0:43:06
Number of People = 500
Number of People Susceptible = 424
Number of People Exposed = 71
Number of People Infectious = 5
Number of People Recovered = 0
Seed Infectiousness Start = -15:40:11
Seed Infectiousness Duration = 31:46:32
Number of Secondary Infections = 75
Mean Number of Contacts per Person = 282.0
Standard Deviation of Number of Contacts per Person = 27.7
Mean Cumulative Contact Time per Person = 51.4 sec
Standard Deviation of Cumulative Contact Time per Person = 72.9 sec

Fig. 5. Environment for contagion spread simulation showing enclosure (shaded) and attraction points. Obstacles or cutouts have been added inside the enclosure.

Fig. 6. Directed motion example using attraction points.

Fig. 7. Uniform mixing example without attraction points.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In the current simulation model there are some simplifying assumptions and limitations. The agents involved are captive in the enclosure during the entire simulation run. No new agents may enter and none may leave. This may be appropriate for some events but not others and may lead to a higher number of secondary infections. On the other hand, only one infectious seed is introduced which may also be unrealistic in some cases. Distance calculations and movements are grid-based which is a trade-off to improve run-times reducing the check for contacts from $O(n^2)$ to $O(n)$ where n is the number of agents. Nonetheless, the tool is useful for exploring the notion that the physical space layout at mass gatherings could be used to mitigate the spread of a contagion.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This material is based upon work supported by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science, DHS, and the CDC. The author would like to express his gratitude to Drs. Jeanette

Rainey and Yao-Hsuan Chen at the CDC and Dr. Jiangye Yuan at ORNL for their suggestions and feedback.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Detels. (2016, June 25). Epidemiology: the foundation of public health [Online]. Available: http://www.ph.ucla.edu/epi/faculty/detels/PH150/Detels_Epidemiology.pdf
- [2] J.J. Rainey et al. (2014, October 24). Estimating contact rates at a mass gathering by using video analysis: a proof-of-concept project [Online]. Available: <http://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1471-2458-14-1101>
- [3] D.B. Koch and P.W. Payne, "An incident management preparedness and coordination toolkit," Proc. IEEE Global Humanitarian Technology Conf., Seattle, WA, 2012, pp. 31-35.
- [4] M. Haran (2009, December). An introduction to models for disease dynamics [Online]. Available: <http://www.unc.edu/~rls/s940/samsidisdyntut.pdf>
- [5] D.J. Toth et al. (2015, June 10). The role of heterogeneity in contact timing and duration in network models of influenza spread in schools [Online]. Available: <http://rsif.royalsocietypublishing.org/content/12/108/20150279>
- [6] D.J. Toth, Electronic supplementary material, unpublished.
- [7] T. Germann, Los Alamos National Laboratory report, unpublished.